

PERCEPTION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE SPEECH AS AN INSTRUMENT OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION. THE ROLE OF LISTENING IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In this article, the concept of listening and the features of its speech perception are taken as an example of speech spoken in a foreign language. Listening is defined and analyzed as the complex perceptual thinking involved in perceiving, understanding, and actively processing information in spoken communication.*

Keywords: *listening, perception, perceptual thinking, analysis, synthesis, acoustic signal, linguistic and extralinguistic knowledge, hearing, mental mnemonic activity, sound information.*

The term “listening” appeared in the teaching literature relatively recently: the term “listening” was first introduced by the American psychologist John Brown in 1930 in his work “Teaching Auditory English”. However, the concept of listening is very multifaceted, there is no single concept that explains this concept, so there are many definitions of this process. Here are some of them: According to E.I. Passov: “Listening is understanding speech by ear or listening with understanding” [8, 166].

N.D. Galskova and N.I. Ghez defines listening as follows: “Listening is complex perceptual thinking - a mnemonic activity associated with the perception, understanding and active processing of information in a speech message” [5, 335]. Some researchers define the concept of “listening” somewhat differently: “the process of perceiving, concentrating and determining the meaning of verbal and visual stimuli” [4, 35].

Listening is also defined as “analysis by synthesis”, based on the theory of speech perception as “an analytical and synthetic process of processing an acoustic signal, leading to an understanding of the perceived information” [7, 27]. Analyzing the research of foreign methodologists, we are faced with the opinion of G. Bank that listening is an active process of interpreting an audio message, based on the linguistic and extralinguistic knowledge of the listener [1]. According to M. Pedi, “listening is an active and dynamic process of concentration, perception, interpretation, memorization and response to expressed (verbal and nonverbal) requests, problems and external information” [2, 16].

Foreign researchers also use the concept of “hearing,” which is understood as the physiological process of speech perception, but from the above definitions it can be determined that listening is a more complex process than just listening. Listening is the ability to distinguish sounds, combine them into semantic complexes and store them in memory while listening. The process of perception occurs at a natural pace characteristic of the language being studied, in the process of mixing natural verbal and non-verbal interactions.

Listening as a type of speech is presented in modern didactics as an ideal (intangible) means of oral learning, a method of mastering the linguocultural aspects of language related to

understanding the material, logic of thought and speech culture. This type of speech activity is also considered in the theoretical foundations of education in connection with the development of perception as a mental function in education, which determines the acquisition of knowledge in the educational activities of students. Listening is a cognitive mental mnemonic activity - perceptual - perception, reception, perception is carried out; mental, since its action is associated with basic mental operations: analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, etc. Mnemonic - because the selection and assimilation of information symbols, image formation, recognition.

Although there are various definitions of the concept of listening, these definitions can be summarized as follows: listening is a process whose main stages are the perception, understanding and direct interpretation of audio information, and the basis of this process is the desire of the listener. to understand the audio message. Listening is an active conscious speech and thought process aimed at recognizing, perceiving, understanding and interpreting an incoming message. A person receives most of the information through the auditory canal and technical communication channels, as in verbal communication, therefore listening is the basis of communication, and mastery of oral communication begins with it.

It is known that listening is not only receiving a message, but also preparing a response to what is heard in the form of internal speech, therefore speaking and listening are two interrelated tools of oral communication. N.I. According to Jinkin, "To learn to understand speech, you must speak and judge your understanding by how your speech is perceived. Understanding is formed in the process of speaking, and speaking is formed in the process of understanding" [6, 370]. Therefore, we can say that listening prepares speech, and speaking helps shape the perception of speech through hearing.

Thus, listening is closely related to the ability to communicate with native speakers, plays an important role in language learning and is a more complex process than speaking, reading and writing.

Learning to understand speech by ear is a complex process that requires maximum attention and concentration from the student, therefore, in the methodology of teaching foreign languages, much attention is paid to listening. In addition to its main, actually communicative, function, listening performs many pedagogical and auxiliary functions. It stimulates students' speech activity, helps manage the educational process, helps them get acquainted with a new language and speech materials, promotes the formation of skills and abilities in all types of speech activity, helps maintain the achieved level of speech, and increases the effectiveness of feedback.

Most methods emphasize that listening is a very important skill, without which communication is impossible. In modern foreign language programs, the main goal is to develop students' abilities:

- Understanding the interlocutor's speech, even if there are unfamiliar words;
- Understanding of authentic audio texts of varying levels of complexity;
- Fully understand the content of the text and be able to highlight the main information in it.

It is true that listening is an important and complex type of speech activity, which should be given sufficient attention in the first stages of foreign language lessons. In the process of learning a foreign language, you need the ability to listen, as well as the ability to speak and express your thoughts and wishes. Without the ability to listen, a person cannot understand the speech of his interlocutor, the speaker, therefore a successful communication process is impossible without the ability to listen [3, 419]. In addition, listening prepares speech, since it is not only the

perception of a message, but also the preparation of a response to the words of the interlocutor. Listening also has educational significance, has a developmental effect on the student, and develops his memory, especially auditory memory.

REFERENCES

1. Buck G. Assessment of listening / G. Buck. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001. - 288 pp.
2. Purdy M. What are they listening to? / M. Purdy // Listening in everyday life: Personal and professional approach / ed. D. Borisov, M. Purdy. - Lanham: University Press of America, 1991. - pp. 3–19.
3. Turdieva N. Yu., Akbarkhanov S. S. IT technologies in teaching foreign languages, distance education, electronic digital education // State Automobile Inspectorate. 2024. No. Special issue 19. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/it-technologies-in-teaching-foreign-languages-distance-education-electron-digital-education>
4. Wolvin A. D. Listening / A. D. Wolvin, K. G. Coakley. - Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill, 1996. Pp. 35.
5. Galskova N.D. Theory of teaching foreign languages: Linguodidactics and methodology / N.D. Galskova, N.I. Guez. - M.: Publishing house "Academy", 2006. - 335 p.
6. Jhinkin N.I. Mechanism / N.I. Jinkin. - M.: Publishing house Acad. ped. Sciences of the RSFSR, 1958. - 370 p.
7. Kolker Ya.M. Training for superior perception of English speech: practice / Ya.M. Kolker, E.S. Ustinova. - M.: Academy, 2002. - 336 p.
8. Obdalova O.A. Listening as a means of teaching foreign language communication to natural science students
9. The faculties at the initial stage: abstract. dissertstion. candidate ped. sciences: 13.00.02 / Obdalova Olga Andreevna; - Tomsk, 2001. - 209 p.